

THERMOPLASTIC SANDWICH SHEETS WITH GLASS FABRIC REINFORCED FACINGS AND RANDOM-IN-PLANE ORIENTED GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED CORES

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ABSTRACT

For economical reasons metal constructions which cannot be replaced by laminate sheets, might be replaced by a new type of thermoplastic sandwich sheet with glass fabric reinforced facings and random-in-plane oriented glass fibre reinforced cores. This paper will give an overview on the manufacturing, material design and forming behaviour of sheets with this new sandwich structure. The influence of core volume ratio on flexural stiffness, flexural strength, and impact energy behaviour will show the potential for the use in large-scaled parts in the automotive industry.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composites with thermoplastic matrix materials like polypropylene (PP), polyethylene terephthalate (PETP), polybutylene terephthalate (PBTP), and nylon (PA) are of interest for the high speed processing industry with cycle times below 1 minute. Many glassfabric reinforced laminates are still at a development stage and it is not proven that these sheet composites will have a chance to replace metal structures in automotive applications, because of high material costs resulting from the necessary production steps in the manufacturing of the glass yarn, finishing, weaving, impregnation, and consolidation of the glass fabrics in the double belt press [1].

Typical parts which could be replaced in the automotive industry are large-scaled and have critical requirements on flexural stiffness, flexural strength, and impact energy behaviour. A reduction of material costs and the fulfilment of the high demands on the mechanical properties can be achieved by the replacement of laminate material in the core with less expensive random-in-plane oriented glass fibre reinforced material. The different material properties of core and facings in the obtained sandwich sheets are much better adapted to the external loads than the material properties of homogeneous glass fabric reinforced sheets. A result could be, that for economical reasons, metal constructions which cannot be replaced by laminate sheets, might be replaced by sandwich sheets.

LAYER STRUCTURE WITH 2 COMPOSITE MATERIALS

The basic structure of the sandwich laminate is shown in Fig. 1. Placing the glass fabric reinforcement in the facings improves the bending and impact behaviour of the whole laminate.

Figure 1. Basic structure of a thermoplastic sandwich sheet provided with glassfabric reinforced facings and glass reinforced core

The random-in-plane oriented glass fibre reinforced material in the core allows for the necessary handling and forming behaviour of heated sheets and reduces the volume ratio of the expensive face material because of its relatively high material properties. The use of one thermoplastic matrix material both in the facings and in the core has the advantage of perfect adhesion built through the consolidation process in the double belt press and later in the forming process. By using a lower glass content in the core with the sandwich structure, higher weight specific properties can be reached than with homogeneous laminates. Compared with conventional sandwich structures which have foamed core materials [2], this sandwich structure can be achieved in the final product by just one forming step within less than 1 minute.

Like homogeneous laminates, the sandwich sheets can be produced with a double belt press. Core material can consist of new glass mat reinforced thermoplastics and/or recycling material of glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic production scrap or of parts after their life cycle. Fig. 2 shows a possible concept to produce glass fabric reinforced sandwich sheets with recycling material in the core.

Figure 2. Manufacturing of the sandwich sheets with recycling material in the core using the double belt press

MATERIAL DESIGN

To make best use of sandwich materials, guidelines are needed for the material design problem in which core and face thicknesses are specified. The main advantages of the sandwich structure arise because the less expensive core material with a lower density enables the panel thickness to be increased for the same weight and material costs. The increase in thickness leads to a higher flexural rigidity of the panel if the material is designed properly.

The introduced sandwich design method is concerned with the calculation and optimization of the weight and cost specific flexural stiffness and flexural strength properties in terms of face and core properties. Shear deformations in bending can be disregarded because the considered core materials are stiff in shear. Using the classical beam bending theory it is assumed that transverse strains and stresses are negligible. Further it is assumed that the face and core materials are linearly elastic to failure. The failure of the sandwich beam is defined by reaching the face material failure stress (the lowest of the tensile strength, the compressive strength or the face wrinkling stress) in the beam surface $z = \pm h/2$. The considered profile of strain and normal stresses of the sandwich beam at failure are shown in Fig. 3 [3].

Figure 3. Profile of strain normal tension by bending a sandwich beam

For a weight respectively cost specific optimized flexural rigidity of the sandwich material Eqn (1) is obtained. The optimum core volume ratio for a cost respectively weight specific optimized flexural strength satisfies the cubic Eqn (2).

$$\varphi_{c,opt} = \sqrt{\frac{1-c}{1-E_c/E_f}} \tag{1}$$

$$\varphi_{c,opt}^3 - \frac{3\varphi_{c,opt}^2}{1-c} + \frac{2}{1-E_c/E_f} = 0 \tag{2}$$

- $\varphi_{c,opt}$ optimum volume ratio of core material
- c constant for weight specific optimization: ρ_c/ρ_f ratio of core and face densities
- constant for cost specific optimization: κ_c/κ_f ratio of core and face material costs
- E_c/E_f ratio of elastic moduli of core and face material

Fig. 4 shows a design chart based on Eqns (1) and (2). After the determination of the optimum core volume ratio the necessary sheet thickness can be calculated by formulas of the classical sandwich beam bending theory to achieve the required flexural stiffness or strength [4].

Figure 4. Design chart for cost and weight specific optimization of sandwich sheets [4]

It has to be assumed that the volume ratio of the core material is varied by the number of fabric layers per facing n and the thickness h of the sandwich laminate. Therefore the closest achievable approach to the theoretical optimized core volume ratio and sandwich sheet thickness has to be chosen. With the area density of textile fabric m_A , the volume ratio of core material φ_c , the density of textile glass ρ_g and the glass volume ratio in the facings $\varphi_{g,f}$ the relation between sheet thickness and core volume ratio is given by Eqn (3):

$$h = \frac{2n m_A}{(1 - \varphi_c) \rho_g \varphi_{g,f}} \quad (3)$$

Using representative values equation (3) is put into a graphical chart, see Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Thickness h of the sandwich structure as function of core volume ratio φ_c and number n of fabric layers per facing

DETERMINATION OF BENDING PROPERTIES AND IMPACT BEHAVIOUR

3 point bending tests and impact penetration tests with glass fabric reinforced polyamide 12 sandwich material (glass content = 52 vol.%) show the influence of the material design on the flexural properties and the impact behaviour. The core material of the tested sandwich specimens consists of regranulated production scrap of parts which are made of glass fabric reinforced polyamide 12 face material. This structure allows for a production integrated recycling.

BENDING STRENGTH AND STIFFNESS

The measured bending properties are compared with calculations made using the classical 1-dimensional beam bending theory.

Fig. 6 shows the measured decrease of the flexural strength with increasing core volume respectively recycling volume ratio. For the calculated curve it is assumed that failure arises when the tensional strain at failure of the face material is reached. The elastic behaviour of the two different composite materials building the sandwich structure is described using secants in the tensile diagram to consider the degressive stress-strain behaviour. The elastic modulus of the core material is chosen as secant between $\epsilon_{c,1} = 0$ and the strain at failure $\epsilon_{c,2} = 0,58\%$. The elastic modulus of the facing is determined as secant between $\epsilon_{f,1} = 0,58\%$ and the strain at failure $\epsilon_{f,2} = 1,70\%$.

flexural strength

Figure 6. Influence of the core material ratio on the 3-point bending strength

The results of the bending tests and the calculated influence of the core volume ratio on the flexural stiffness are shown in Fig. 7. The measured flexural moduli are determined as secants between 0,05 and 0,25% strain. The tensional moduli of the 2 composite materials, which are the basis for the calculated curve, are determined within the same strain range.

flexural modulus

Figure 7. Influence of the core material ratio on the 3-point bending moduli

MULTIAXIAL IMPACT BEHAVIOUR

The multiaxial impact behaviour of rigid plastics is determined in the instrumented puncture test (ISO 6603-2), see Fig. 8. The total penetration energy is the area under the curve in the force-deformation diagram. With core volume ratios of 20% and 40% the behaviour of the flat specimens is similar to the tested homogeneous laminate specimens. The drop in the peak force leads to a drop in the energy to peak force of 10% respectively 20%. The second peak of the curves with 0%, 20% and 40% recycling material occurs due to the formation of the hole during the penetration of the steel striker.

Specimens with core volume ratios of 60% and 80 % absorb less energy due to dips in the rising part of the force-deformation diagram. The recycling material absorbs the lowest amount of energy. It is remarkable that the absorbed energy is more than doubled with just one fabric layer as face reinforcement.

Force

Figure 8. Multiaxial impact behaviour of 2,2 mm thick glassfabric reinforced polyamide 12 sandwich specimens with regrated production scrap as core material

FORMING BEHAVIOUR

The difference in the forming behaviour of thermoplastic sheets to laminate structure and to sandwich structure is investigated in an isothermal deep drawing test [6], see Fig. 9.

Figure 9. Deep drawing test of 1,1 mm glass fabric reinforced polyamide 12 sheets with homogeneous laminate structure and with sandwich structure

As soon as isothermal condition is reached ($T_{Oven} = T_{Tool} = T_{Sheet} = 240^{\circ}C$), the vacuum pump system applies the forming pressure of 0,005 MPa in the cavity which has a diameter of 50 mm. The stamp and the device for holding down the sheet prevent wrinkling during the forming process. The depth is measured by an inductive length measurement system.

The sandwich sheet shows a higher forming degree because the introduced forming force per fabric layer is higher due to the smaller amount of fabric layers in the sheet. Introduced tensile forces, which are not parallel to the warp or weft direction, cause a larger distortion of the fabric, which is called the intraply shear effect. Because a laminate, impregnated with resin, has to fulfil the constant volume requirement, the thickness of the laminate increases during intraply shearing. Due to the constant gap width between stamp and cavity, the increase in thickness results in an increase of surface pressure. Higher surface pressure causes higher friction between weft and warp yarns. Due to the lower amount of fabric layers in the sandwich sheet and due to the flow pressable behaviour of the core material, the surface pressure and hence the friction in cross-over points is lower than in the homogeneous laminate. The relative movement of laminate layers ("interply slipping") is favoured at lower surface pressure.

CONCLUSIONS

Glass fabric reinforced thermoplastic sandwich sheets with random-in-plane oriented glass fibre reinforced cores have a potential for use as large-scaled parts in the high speed manufacturing industry which has critical requirements on flexural rigidity and impact behaviour. The sandwich sheet structure can be manufactured with the double belt press

technology and offers the possibility to use recycling material in the core. A design method for defining the optimum core volume ratio is shown. With a lower core density the sandwich material will have higher weight and cost specific properties than a homogeneous laminate. The results of 3-point bending tests prove the calculation method with the 1 dimensional beam-bending theory as a useful approach. Glassfabric reinforced sandwich sheets with up to 40 % recycling material in the core show in the multiaxial impact test a similar impact behaviour to homogeneous laminates with slightly lower force-levels. An isothermal deep drawing test shows that with the same forming force, sandwich sheets have a higher maximum forming degree than homogeneous laminates.

Further investigations of the the forming behaviour of advanced composites are needed to gain more fundamental knowledge about the complex forming processes, which determine the basis for the simulation of the forming process. The forming technology and tools can then be adapted to the forming behaviour. The design of the composite sheets can be adjusted to local different material requirements. This possibility of material adjustment is generally the high potential of advanced composites.

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